

ENVIRONMENTAL DURABILITY OF KENAF FIBRE REINFORCED UNSATURATED POLYESTER COMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

Nowadays overusing the fossil fuels and resource brings out irreversible impact on global environment. At this moment, “eco-design” is becoming a philosophy to guide next generation of materials and products. Therefore, in order to solve the ecological concern and sustainable living problem, renewed interest in developing composite material from environmentally friendly nonpetroleum-based natural fibers is increasing. Natural fibers possess advantages over synthetic or manmade fibers due to its abundance, biodegradability, CO₂ neutrality, excellent price/performance ratio and comparable specific strength properties.

Recently, one of the most widely used natural fibers is kenaf, which has been successfully incorporated in variety of applications especially for composite reinforcement [1]. Kenaf is well known as a cellulosic source from annual kenaf plant with both economic, ecological advantages and unique mechanical properties such as high tensile strength and stiffness, impact resistance and bending flexibility, which can be grown under a wide range of climatic conditions with high speed and relatively little care. In Malaysia, frantic effort has been made through the national kenaf research and development program to make kenaf an industrial crop and commercially viable product [2]. A serious of research works had been conducted one by one on Malaysian cultivated kenaf with a view to make kenaf a potential and economically viable plant to be utilized more wisely and economically [3-4].

The mechanical properties, fibre loading and compatibiliser addition effect of kenaf fiber reinforced composites have been reported in

previous literatures. M. R. Ishak et al. investigated mechanical properties of kenaf bast and core fibre reinforced unsaturated composites, in which demonstrated kenaf bast fibre's higher mechanical properties than kenaf core fibre composites and 20wt% was the optimum fibre content for highest tensile strength achievement for both bast and core composites [4]; A. Hao et al. studied mechanical properties of kenaf/polypropylene nonwoven composites (KPNC) as interior parts under various loading and found out the KPNCs were not sensitive to the notch in tensile test but sensitive to the strain rates [5]; M.Z. Ahmad Thirmizir et al. evaluated kenaf bast fiber (KBF)'s loading and maleated PBS compatibiliser's addition on performance of the composite under 6 months natural weathering ageing in a tropical climate by color change analysis, FTIR spectroscopy analysis and SEM examination [6]; T. T. Law et al. paid attention to the water absorption and dimensional stability of short kenaf fiber-filled polypropylene composites treated with maleated polypropylene (MAPP), which revealed MAPP's significant improvement in compatibility between fiber and matrix, reduced water absorption as well as thickness swelling in the composites [7].

Outdoor applications of natural fiber composite is raising concerns in terms of their durability, including UV resistance, moisture resistance and extreme temperature withstand and dimensional stability. As well known, natural environment degradation is the essential method to investigate composite's durability during their service life. Thus far, there seems still lack of knowledge and study reporting on kenaf fiber reinforced unsaturated polyester composite's environmental degradable and durable behavior upon exposure into apparently

different geographic environment conditions. In general, the vital function of this study was to characterize the durability of KUNCs under subtropical marine monsoon climate with mild temperature in Shanghai (China), continental monsoon climate with extreme cold temperature (Harbin) and mild sea climate Kyoto (Japan) by changes in physical and mechanical properties.

2 Materials and Fabrication

2.1 Materials

Bulkier kenaf nonwoven fabrics with gram weight range from 1300- 1800 g/m² was produced by Dr Rahmatullah Holdings Sdn.Bhd., Malaysia. Specially, needle-punching technique (GROZ-BECKERT) was applied to form fiber entanglement and 3D fiber orientation by an array of barbed needles penetration through kenaf nonwoven web, as shown in Fig.1 punching line was very apparent appeared on the Kenaf mat surface. In addition, degradation temperature and density of kenaf fiber in this study are 265.17 °C and 1.35 g/cm³ respectively. Unsaturated polyester and methyl ethyl ketone peroxide (MEKP) catalyst were employed as the matrix system in the ratio of 100 : 0.7, which supplied by Showa Highpolymer Co. Ltd., Japan.

2.2 Composites fabrication

Predetermined size of kenaf nonwoven fabrics with 150 mm X 250 mm and comparable bigger size of folded PET film box were prepared prior to molding.

Firstly, kenaf fabric was impregnated into mixed matrix system filled in PET film box assisted by vacuum system without heating for 20 minutes. Afterwards, the molded panels were kept at the room temperature with certain weight for 24 hours curing period followed by 2 hours post-cure in an air-convection oven at 100°C.

In order to obtain good mechanical performance, similar fiber weight fraction of 16% (reported by M. R. Ishak et. [4]) were decided and different composite panel thickness was also controlled by spacers respectively owing to kenaf mat varied unit

area gram weight with a average thickness range from 7mm to 8mm.

Figure1. Original punched Kenaf mat material and fabricated panel sheet

3 Environmental aging and degradation

Samples with the size corresponded to ASTM standards for predetermined mechanical tests were prepared to place upon subtropical marine monsoon climate with mild temperature in Shanghai (China), continental monsoon climate with extreme cold

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temperature (Harbin) and mild sea climate Kyoto (Japan) simultaneously in a absolutely exposure condition up to 2160 hours. During ageing period, characteristic parameters of degradation environment were recorded such as temperature, relative humidity and amount of precipitation based on the local weather station. Mass change of the samples was recorded using an electronic balance followed by moisture uptake calculation. The moisture uptake expressed in percent weight gain, W_c %, is Eq. (1).

Equation:

$$W_c \% = \frac{(W_D - W_O)}{W_O} * 100 \quad (1)$$

Where W_O and W_D are the mass of the specimen before and after ageing in a natural dried condition.

4 Testing Method

4.1 Mechanical Testing

Tensile tests, 3-point bending tests and fracture toughness test-single edge notch bending (SENB) were carried out for non-degraded and after 2160 hours (3 months) ageing samples by universal testing machine (Type 4206) to determine aged mechanical properties. At the same time, tensile, flexural and single notch bending test were in accordance to the ASTM D5083, ASTM D 790-3 and ASTM D5045-99 respectively. Especially, SENB test was performed with 10mm/min loading rate, during which non-notched specimens was also prepared for deflection correction in order to calculate toughness G_{Ic} . Additionally, Izod impact test was performed on the Impact tester (Toyoseiki) with pendulum 5.5J in accordance with ADTM D 256-05.

4.2 Observation

Cross-section, fiber bundle and crack development of KUNC for both before and after ageing were observed by a Reflection-Type Optical Microscope. Selected specimens were embedded

with epoxy resin following by 12 hours' resin cure in room temperature and then polished by a polishing machine (Doctor-Lab, ML-180) before observation.

The fracture surfaces after tensile and Izod tests were also inspected by a field emission scanning electron microscope (Hitachi, S-4200) (SEM) with a focus on fiber pull-out performance to characterize their interfacial bonding and relationship with test results. Gold was sputtered onto the specimens for electron conductivity before SEM observation.

5 Results and Conclusions

5.1 Environmental degradation condition record and sample's weight change ratio

Real-time natural weather conditions among Kyoto (Japan), Shanghai (China) and Harbin (China) were recorded based on local meteorological agency's report everyday during 3 months environmental degradation period. As shown in Tab.1, total precipitation, average temperature and average relative humidity were summarized and tabulated. It was clearly to found that Shanghai city received the least total precipitation amount during specific degradation period than other two degradation positions. Especially, Harbin city's average temperature presented an extreme cold condition. However, there was not the big difference in the average relative humidity among predetermined 3 positions.

Weight change ratio of the samples plotted with specific degradation position was gathered in Fig.2. It was deserved to note that samples aged in Harbin represented the biggest weight gain ratio, which was around 8 times of samples degraded in other two positions'. Furthermore, even if the samples were placed into two different positions (Shanghai & Kyoto) with respective climate condition, their weight gain ratios were nearly the same. Combined the environment condition phenomena with experimental weight change ratio result, it was indicated the significant weight gain in samples after 3 months degradation in Harbin may caused by precipitation absorption from deteriorate interphase.

As the samples placed upon extreme cold environment (Harbin), composite samples internal (fiber and matrix) inhomogeneous shrinkage deformation resulted in micro-cracks.

Time Period	Total Precipitation (mm)			Average Temperature (°C)			Average Relative Humidity (%)		
	Shanghai	Harbin	Kyoto	Shanghai	Harbin	Kyoto	Shanghai	Harbin	Kyoto
2012/12/20-31	12	21	60	4.9	-22.2	5.0	80	79	70
2013/1/1-31	47	96	41	4.4	-21.0	3.9	67	69	66
2013/2/1-28	66	93	96	6.7	-16.4	4.5	73	65	67
2013/3/1-20	53	40	63	11.0	-9.4	9.5	62	64	57
Summary	177	250	259	6.8	-17.3	5.7	71	69	65

Tab.1 Environmental Degradation Condition Record

Figure.2 Weight change after 3 months environmental degradation

5.2 Mechanical testing results

5.2.1 Tensile Test

Fig.3 displayed the typical stress-strain curves comparison among samples of non-degrade and 3 months degraded in specific environments. It revealed degraded samples had decreased tensile strength and nearly the same strain. Additionally, retention ratios of tensile strength after ageing in respective position were also compared for degradation degree explanation in Fig.4. It demonstrated samples degraded in Shanghai still had around 96% retention of strength; on the contrast, tensile strength of samples aged both in Kyoto and Harbin represented an apparent deteriorate effect with 15% and 26% dropping.

Figure.3 Typical Stress-Strain curves comparison among samples of non-degrade and 3 months degradation in different environments

Figure.4 Retention of tensile strength (%)

5.2.2 3-point bending test

Both flexural modulus and strength experimental results of samples before and after ageing were illustrated in Fig.5. As shown in Fig.5, bending modulus didn't make a big difference with a flat trend of plotting curve. However, sample's bending strength after degradation presented varying deduction level, in which samples degraded in Kyoto showed the largest decrement (25%). It can be supposed to be the deteriorated fiber bundle and changed crack development in KUNC, which also can be examined and verified in following microscope inspection.

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Figure.5 Bending modulus and strength comparison among samples of non-degrade and 3 months degradation in different environments

5.2.3 Fracture toughness test

Fracture toughness K_{Ic} and G_{Ic} were calculated based on the max load (P_{max}) reflected in Fig.6 in accordance with equations defined in ASTM D5045-99. Summarized K_{Ic} and G_{Ic} results of samples before and after ageing were displayed in histogram Fig.7, from which aged KUNC sample's deteriorate resistance to crack propagation and decreased crack-growing energy were clarified clearly. As the same consideration with sample's largest weight gain ratio aged in Harbin mentioned forgoing, shrinkage micro-crack/fracture led by extreme cold temperature brought out a most serious deteriorated fracture toughness property for aged KUNC samples in Harbin with 10% decreasing rate.

Relation between weight gain ratio and fracture toughness property change of samples after ageing were plotted in Fig.8 as well. It demonstrated moisture absorption played an important role in KUNC sample's ageing performance related to fracture toughness. Aged KUNC sample's resistance for crack propagation and crack-growing energy decreased with increasing weight gain ratio. Because during degradation period, samples were easily to absorbed water and moisture from surrounded environment and that status led to weaker reinforcement fiber and deteriorate fiber/matrix interphase.

Figure.6 Load-Deflection curves for single notched samples of non-degrade and 3 months degradation in different environments

Figure.7 Fracture toughness comparison among single notched samples of non-degrade and 3 months degradation in different environments

Figure.8 Relation between weight gain ratio and fracture toughness property change of KUNC samples after ageing

5.2.4 Izod Impact Test

Absorbed energy of non-degraded and degraded samples after pendulum izod impact test was summarized and compared in Fig.9. It was very interesting to find two changing trend after 3 months environmental degradation. For the samples degraded in Harbin city displayed nearly 10% decreasing in absorbed energy. However, samples placed in rest two cities both showed around 15% up of absorbed energy conversely. Combining with their weight change ratio, samples degraded in HIT with largest weight increasing ratio may affect the bonding status between fiber and matrix, therefore, weak interface led to lower absorbed energy during pendulum impact test. While, slight water absorption in samples degraded in KIT and DH may release the fiber, which make composite sample stronger to resistant pendulum impact process.

Figure.9 Absorbed energy comparison during izod test among non-degraded and degraded composite samples

5.3 Observation

5.3.1 Morphology of KUNC and bending crack development

Taking KUNC samples aged in Kyoto and Shanghai as an example, optical images of fabricated KUNC before and after ageing were shown in Figure.10, in which punched fibers and entangled fiber morphology can be examined easily. It is noteworthy that departed microfiber characteristic and cracked polymer trace existed in aged fiber bundle differed from non-degraded one in enlarged photographs. It is considered that general ultraviolet damage on the resin close to the fiber/matrix interphase and absorbed moisture's expansion effect on deteriorate interphase during

environmental degradation period led to final microfiber's depart.

As mentioned forgoing, bending strength of aged samples in Kyoto displayed 25% decreasing. Here, sample's bending crack development before and after ageing were compared in Fig.11. Referring to the non-degrade KUNC sample, crack developed along outside of fiber bundle after bending. On the contrary, degraded sample's crack went through the interphase between microfibers. Different fracture performances of aged bending sample strongly pointed out their deteriorate interphases and corresponded different crack development mechanism.

Figure.10 Cross section observation of KUNC before and after ageing

Figure.11 Bending crack development of KUNC before and after ageing

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5.3.2 Fracture surface inspection

Based on the fracture surface observations after Izod impact test, fiber ruptures on the crack surface have been observed in non-degraded and degraded composites. As the same with original sample, degraded samples also displayed a rough fracture surface with some long and short fibers pulling-out performance. (Shown in Figure.12)

Figure.12 Fracture surface observation of KUNC after Izod test for non-degraded and degraded composite samples

Sample's fracture surface inspection with respect to fiber pull-out performance after tensile test was also conducted and displayed in Fig.13. According to Fig.13, a good interphase between fiber and matrix and comparative short fiber pull-out behavior in non degrade sample were examined as kenaf fiber's rough surface. On the contrast, accompanied

with fiber pull-out performance, aged fractured sample also showed a comparative apparent crack in the matrix originating from pull-out region. Owing to ultraviolet damage on polymer, weak matrix resin was considered to be easily fractured with fiber pulling out performance, which may affect stress transfer during tensile test leading to dropped strength.

Figure.13 Fracture surface observation of KUNC after tensile test for non-degraded and degraded composite samples

5.4 Conclusions

In this study, kenaf/unsaturated polyester nonwoven composite (KUNC)'s weight change ratio and related aged mechanical properties after 3 months environmental degradation in three different climate conditions (Kyoto, Shanghai and Harbin) were investigated.

Firstly, KUNC's durability behavior on physical characteristic upon three different geographies' environmental degradation were examined and clarified including matrix resin's embrittlement, microfibers' depart in fiber bundle and weight gain ratio because of moisture absorption.

Eventually, relation between physical property's change and deteriorate mechanical performance was summarized. Simultaneously,

different natural environment weathering conditions' varying ageing effects on KUNC were compared and discussed. It was demonstrated that weight gain owing to the absorbed moisture from environment made a big difference on tensile, bending strength and fracture toughness for aged samples. On basis of fiber bundle's observation, degraded effects comparison among those three specific positions indicated extreme cold temperature played an important role in deteriorating process excepting of total precipitation amount from natural weathering.

5.5 Future Research

In order to get a well knowledge of KUNC's durability behavior upon different environmental climate conditions, samples' exposition upon more extreme environments with longer degradation periods will be concentrated to study in the next step. Consequently, KUNC's processing, surface treatment and priority can be guided efficiently for widely utilization for realistic construction application field.

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